

Additional information 1: The hybrid sequence based on TuYV isolates Salzlandkreis-2_16 and Kreis Stormarn_16 used as a reference for mapping the Illumina reads

CAAAGAAACCAGGAGGGAATCCTAAGTTGATGCAATTTGTCGCTCACGATAACTTTTACAC
CTCTAGAAGTCAGGAAAGTCAGATACCTCCACNCAAAGCAAGTAACGTTTCTTTTAGCAG
GTCNTTTGCTTAACATCNAACAATTNGTAAAAGCAATCAAAGAGCGCAACAATGANTTCA
AAACTGANNTTTTTCTTCGCTCTCTGCTCTATCAGCTTCCTCTCCACCTCGGAGACCACATC
CACGANGANGTCAGGAAGTCCATACTTGCNCCTGAACCAGAGCTTTGTGCCTGGTTCTCTT
TACAAACGGGATATGCTCCCGCCTCCACCTCAGGCCGTGTTAACTTANACGTGCCAGGAAC
CAAGACCTCTCGCNGAAGAATCATAACAACGATCTTTTGCAGCAATTTCTCAGAAAAGCTC
AAGNGATTTCCAGAATGCCTATTCGGTAGCCTTGAGTATTTCCAGCGANTTCTATCAACATG
GACTAAAGACGTTGAAAGACGTATCTTTTCTCGCTGTCGAGAAATTCCTTTGGGGTCTGAC
ACGCTTGTGGAGCTCGCTAATCTTGGCGAGCTTCTCCGCGTTATGGTGGTTGGTGAGCAAT
TTCACAACCTCCCGTCTTCTGTCTCGCCTTGCTGTACACTGTTACAAGATTTATGGTGAAGAC
GGTTTCATTTCTTTTGGAGGATTGCCAATCTGGATCATNTCGATTGCTTTCTCACTCCTGAA
GAAATCCTTTTTCAGCTCTTCGGTCTACACCGAAATGTTTGTATGAAAAGGCCATAGACGGT
TTCAAGAGTTTACNATCCCGCAGAGCCCCCAAATCTTGCCTGATTCCCATCACCCACG
CAAGCGGAAACCACGCTGGCTACGCCAGCTGTGTCAAGCTATAACAANGGCGAAAACGCTT
TAATGACGGCAACTCACGTNCTACGTGACTGCCCAATGCTGTAGCTATTTCCGCCAAAGG
GCTTAAGACTCGGATTCACCTCGCTGAATTCAAACAATTGCGAAATCCGACAAAGGTGAT
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GTCATTACAGCNGCCAACCTAGCNAATGCAAAGCATCCATATACTCTTTTGGAGAGAGATG
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CCACACGGAAGGAGGACACTCCGGAAGCCCCTACTTNAATGGTAAAACCATCNTAGGGGT
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ANGAAAAATTTCAAGTCNAAGACTGGAACAAATTGGGNNGATATGGANGANGATGAAGA
CATCTTCTTCGAAAGNANAGAAGATCTNCCGGGAAACGGAGTGCGCGGCGCCGACCGCG
AAACAAACGGAGAAGGCAGCTCCACCCCAAAGACAAACAACGTCGATGGGAAAGAGATG
ATGGAGAAAATAATCTCATCTCTGGTGGGGAANATAAATCTCGNGAACATCGAGAAGAAA
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CCCAAAGAAACAGCCGGAGAGTTCGAAAGATACTTCTCCTCACTCTACNACTGGGAGGTA
CCAACCTCCCCACGTGAGGTCCCCGGCTTCCGTCACTGCGGCAAGCTGCCCAATACTACC
ACCCCAAGCAAAAAGAAGAATCCAGCTGGGGGAAAACCCTCGTCGGAACCATCCCGCG
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GAGCCTGCGACTGCAGGCTTACGGTGGCTGGAACGCGCCAGTCCGCAGAAATACCCTC
TGACGCTGAGAGGGAGCGTGTGATTCAAAGACCGCAGATGTTTACCATNCTTGCCAAAC
AAATGGACCTGCGGCAACCCGAGGAGGAGCACTGACCTGGAACAACCTTCATGATTGATTT
CAAACAGGCGGTGTTCTCGCTGGAGTTCGATGCCGGAATCGGCGTCCCCTATATTGCCTAT
GGCAAGCCACACACCGTGGGTGGGTAGAAGATCAGACACTCCTTCCGGTCTTAGCTCAA
TTGACCTTCATCCGACTACAGAAGATGTTGGAGGTTAGTTTCGAAGATATGGGACCAGAGG
AGCTGATCCAGAACGGTTTGTGCGACCCCATCCGATTATTCGTGAAAGGGGAGCCCCACA
ACAAGCGAAGCTCGATGAAGGCCGCTACCGCCTCATTATGAGCGTTTCCCTCGTGGATCA
ATTGGTAGCCCGGTTCTGTTCCAAAACCAGAACAAGCGGGAATGCCCCTTGGAGGGC
CATCCCCAGTAAACCCGGTTTTGGCTTGTCCACGGACGAGCAAGTGCTGGACTTTGTNAA
AGGTTTGGCCCGTCAAGTAGGCACTACGACAACAGAGGTAGTTGCCAATTGGAAAAATTA
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GATATGATCGTCCGCAATAGACTTACCATCGACCTCAACCCTGTTACAGAAAGATTAAGATC
CTGTTGGTTGAGNTGTGTTTCAAACCTCAGTGNTNTGCCTGAGTGATGGTACCCTTTTAGCC

CAAACCCATCCGGGCGTTCAGAAAAGTGGGAGCTACAATACNTCAAGCTCCAACCTCCCGG
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CCCTCGAGTCCAATCCCGCTGACCTAGCAGCGTACAAAAGACTAGGTTTCAAGGTTGAGG
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AGCGTCCGTTGAACTTCTTTACTCGTGGTTAGTCGACCCCGTGCTACCACAAAAGATACCA
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CCTGAGATCAATCGTTAATGAATACGGTCGTGGGTAGAAGAACAATCAATGGAAGAAGAC
GACCACGGAGGCAAGCACGACGCNCTCAGCGCTCTCAGCCAGTGGTTGTGGTCCAAGCCT
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AACTGTTCTACCAGAGGAGCAGGTTTCGAGCGAGACATTTGTTTTCTCAAAAAGACAATCTC
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CTCCGANGCCTCTTCCAAAATTCCGGTTCATCGCTTACGAGCTGGACCCACACTGTA
CTCAACTCCCTTTCCTCAACTATCAACAAATTCGGGATCACAAAGCCCCGGGAGGAGGGCG
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ATCCTCTACAAAGGCAATGGTTCTTCATCGATAGCTGGTTCTTTCAGAATCACCATAAAGTG
CCAATTCCACAATCCCAAATAGGTAGACGAGGAACCCGGCCCCAGCCCAGGGCCTTCTCC
CTCTCCACAACCCACACCCCAAAAAGAAATATCGTTTTATCGTCTATACTGGAGTNCCTGTG
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GTTTCGNTACATAGAGGACGAGAACATGAACTGGACGAACCTCGATTCCCGATGGTATTCC
CAGAATTCTTTGAAAGCCATCCCGATGATAATAGTACCAGTCCCTCAAGGTGAGTGGACCG
TGGAATTTTCGATGGAGGGGTATCAACCAACCTCAAGTACCACAGATCCTAATAAGGACAA
ACAAGATGGTCTCATTGCATACAATGATGACCTCAAGGAGGGTTGGAATGTGGGGGTTTAT
AATAATGTGGAGATAACCAACAATAAGGCCGACAANACTCTCAAGTACGGCCACCCAGAC
ATGGAACCTCAANAGNTGTCATTTCAATCAAGGNCAGTGTCTGGAAAGAGATGGAGATTG
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GATAGGATTGATAGCCATAGCACTTGATGAACAAGGCTCATCCGGTTCACAANGACAGAA
AGACCAAAGAGAGTTGGGCACTCCATGGCAGTCTCAACCTGGGAGACTATAAACTTACCG
GAGAAGGAAAACCTCCGAGAAATTCGAAACCAGTCAAAGACAAGACTCTAAAACCTCAACC
TAAACAAGGTTTCTCAGATGCTGGTTCTGAAGACAACAAGGAATGGGATTTTACACCCGG
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CTCAGAGATAGAGGAATTGTAGTNGATCCCTCCTTGTGGAAATACCTGACTCACCTCCTC
CGAGAGCGGACCATAAGGACACAGATCCTTGGGCTGAGGTTGAAAGATATAAATCTTCCCA
NAAAGCCCTTGTTCGGCGAGGACACGCGTTCCCGACAATCATCCTTGACAGGAGGTTTCGCT
TGCTGGCGGCAGCCTTAGAAAGCTGAAGCCGGTTACACCGGACGAGTATGAGCAGGCAAA
ACTGAAAGATGANTCNAGACTCCAGTATGAACAGGATCTCGCTGAGTATCACAAGAGTTT
GAAAAGACCCGGAAGCGCGTTAATACCACGNGATGACGGTGAGCTCATGGAGATGGATCC
TTCTCAACGTAAATTGATGAAGAACGCTGGAGTCAACCTTGATAAGTATGGTAGACCAGTT
AGGAAAGGTTTCTCTCTTTCAGGAAATAGTCCCCAGTACTTAACTGGCTCGTTGGTAGT
GATACGAGGCGAAAATCAAACTACCCTTATCTAGCTTTATTTCTATTTAGCTAATAAAGTCA
AGCCAGAGA

Additional information 2: Alignment of the regions missing in the Illumina sequence with the sequences of the other TuYV infections in plants from the same location.

Additional information 3: The almost complete nucleotide sequence of the beet-infecting isolate found in The Netherlands in 2020. The sequence is largely based on Illumina sequencing.

NNNTGCAATTTGTTGCTCACGATAACTTT
CACACTTTAGAAAGTCAGGAAAGTCAGATACCTCCACCCAAAGCAAGTAACGTTTCTTCTAG
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CAAACTGATATTTTTCTTCGCTCTCTGCTCTATCAGCTTCCTCTCCACCTCGGAGACCACA
TCCACGATGATGTCAGGAAGTCCATACTTGCCCCTGAACCAGAGCTTTGTGCCTGGTTCTC
TTTACAAACGGGATATGCTCCCGCTCCACCTCAGGCCGTGTTAACTTATACGTGCCAGGA
ACCAAGACCTCTCGCGGAAGAATCATAACAACGATCTTTTTCGCGAGCGATTCTCAGAAAAGC
TCAAGAGATTTCCAGAATGCCTATTCGGTAGCCTTGAGTATTTCCAGCGATTCTATCAACA
TGGACTAAAGACGTTGAAAGACGATCTTTTCTCGCTGTCGAGAAATTCCTCTGGGGTCTG
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ATTTCACAACTCCCGTCTTCTGTCTCGCCTTGCTGTACTGTTACAAGATTTATGGTGAAG
ATGGTTTCATTTCTTTTGGAGGATTGCCAATCTGGATCATTTCGATTGCTTTCTCACTCCTG
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GTTTCAAGAGTTTCACTATCCACAGAGCCCCCAAATCTTGCCTGATTCCCATCACCCA
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TTAATGACGGCAACCCACGTTCTACGTGACTGCCCCAATGCTGTAGCTATTTCCGCCAAA
GGGCTTAAACTCGGATTCCACTCGCTGAATTCAAAACAATTGCGAAATCCGACAAAGGT
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GAGCCACACGGAAGGAGGACACTCCGGAAGCCCCTACTTTAATGGTAAAACCATTTTAGG
GGTTCATTCAGGTGCCAGTGCTACAGGAAATTACAACCTTGATGGCACCAATCCCGCCCCTC
CCCGGACTCACAAAGTCCGACTTATGTGTTTGAAACCACCGCACCACAAGGAAGAGTTTTC
GCACAAGAAGATATCGCCGAGATCGAAAGATCTCTATGCGCAAGCAGTAGAGAGATCGAA
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AGACATCTTCTTCGAAAGCAGAGAAGATCTGTGCGGAAACGGAGTGCGCGGCGCCGACC
GCGAAACAAACGGAGAAGGCAGCTTCACCCCAAAGACAAACAACGTCGATGGAAAAGA
GATGATGGAGAAAATAATCTCATCTCTGGTGGGGAAGATAAATCTCGGGAACATCGAGAAG
AAAGTGATAGAGGAGATCTCCGCGAAAGCGATGAAAGCTCCAAAATCCCGCCGCAGAAG
AGCCCCAAAGAAACAGCCGGAGAGTTCGAAAGATACTTCTCCTCGCTCTACAGCTGGGAA
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GAAGAGCCTGCGACTGCAGGCTTACGGTGGCTGGAACGCGCCCAGTCCGCAGAAATACC
CTCTGACGCTGAGAGGGAGCGTGTGATTCAAAGACCGCAGATGTTTACCATCCTTGCCA
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TTTCAAACAGGCGGTGTTCTCGCTGGAGTTCGATGCCGGAATCGGCGTCCCCTATATTGCCT
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CAAACAAGCGAAGCTCGATGAAGGCCGCTACCGCCTCATTATGAGCGTTTCCCTCGTGGAT
CAATTGGTGGCCCGGTTCTGTTCCAAAACCAGAACAAGCGGGAAATTGCCCTGTGGAGG
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TCCTGTTGGTTGAGGTGTGTTTCAAACCTCAGTGCTATGCCTGAGTGATGGTACCCTTTTAGC
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GATCAGAGTTATGGCCGCCTTTCATACAGGTGCTGCCTGGGCTATGGCGATGGGCGATGAC
GCCCTCGAGTCCAATCCCGCTGACCTAGCAGCGTACAAAAGACTAGGTTTTCAAGGTTGAG
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GAGGTAGTTTTCAAACCTTAGCCGCTTGTCTCAGTTCTGAACGAGTTGCGGCACGATC
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CACCTGAGATCAATCGTTAATGAATACGGTTCGTGGGTAGAAGAACAATCAATGGAAGAAG
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CCTCTCGGACAACACAACGCCGACCAAGACGACGACGAAGAGGCGGTAACCGGACAGGA
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AGGATCCTCTACAAAGGCAATGGTTCTTCATCGATAGCTGGTTCTTTCAGAATCACCATAAA
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AAGGTTTCGCTACATAGAGGACGAGAACATGAACTGGACGAACCTCGATTCCCGATGGTAT
TCCCAGAATTTCTTGAAAGCCATCCCGATGATAATAGTACCAGTCCCTCAAGGTGAGTGGA
CAGTGGAATTTTCGATGGAGGGGTATCAACCAACCTCAAGTACCACAGATCCTAATAAGGA
CAAACAAGATGGTCTTATTGCATACAATGATGACCTCAAGGAGGGTTGGAATGTTGGGGTT
TATAATAATGTGGAGATAACCAACAATAAGGCCGACAACACTCTCAAGTACGGCCACCCAG
ACATGGAACTCAATAGCTGTCATTTCAATCAAGGACAGTGTCTGGAAAGAGACGGAGATTT
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TTCTCAACGTAAATTGATGAAGAACGCTGGAGTCAACCTTGATAAGTATGGTAGACCAGTT
AGAAAAGGTTTCTCTCTTTCAGGAAATAGTCCCCAGTACTTAACTGGCTCGTTGGTAGT
GATACGAGGCGAAAATCAAACCTACCCTTATCTAGCTTTATTTCTATTTAGCTAATAAAGTCA
AGCCAGAGACATTAACCTGGAACGACTCCGTTTTGCGGATAGGCAACGAGTGTTTTACGC
NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN

Additional information 4: TuYV and BrYV isolates from NCBI together with the virus (BrYV/TuYV) to which it's 5'end and 3'end are most similar to. In case the 5'end and 3'end differ, the location of the breaking point is also given.

GenBank accession number	Virus name in GenBank	5'end mostly similar to	3'end mostly similar to	Year	Host	Country
LC428364	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2014	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Japan
LC428365	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2017	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Japan
MT586572	TuYV	BrYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	Australia
LC428360	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	Japan
LC428361	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2017	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Japan
OM469309	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Australia
NC_016038	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2008	<i>Brassica napus</i>	China
HQ388348	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2008	<i>Brassica napus</i>	China
MZ666129	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2020	<i>Strawberry</i>	China
HQ388350	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2009	<i>Brassica campestris</i>	China
LC428359	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Sinapsis alba</i>	Japan
LC428358	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	Japan
LC428362	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	Japan
KF015269	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2011	<i>Brassica rapa pekinensis</i>	China
JN015068	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2010	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	China
HQ388351	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2009	<i>Brassica campestris</i>	China
LC428363	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2017	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Japan
HQ388349	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2008	<i>Brassica napus</i>	China
KY310572	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Brassica napus</i>	China
MT586571	TuYV	BrYV	BrYV	2004	<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	Australia
MT586573	TuYV	BrYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	Australia
MT586576	TuYV	BrYV	BrYV	2014	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586574	TuYV	BrYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Lens culinaris</i>	Australia
MT586575	TuYV	BrYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Australia
MF314820	BrYV	BrYV	BrYV	2014	<i>Tabacco</i>	China
MK616236	TuYV	BrYV	TuYV	2017	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	China
MK057527	BrYV	BrYV	TuYV	2014	<i>Tabacco</i>	China
KR706247	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2017	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	China
MZ313372	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2017	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	Brazil
MT955608	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2018	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Greece
MT955609	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2018	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Greece
Our Illumina sequence	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2020	<i>Beta vulgaris</i>	Netherlands
OK030771	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MN497803	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
OK030792	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030798	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MN497808	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
OK030791	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030769	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom

OK030785	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030784	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MN497810	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2017	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MT955610	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2018	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Greece
MT955611	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2018	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Greece
OK030788	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MT586582	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2018	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586581	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	Australia
LC701523	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Australia
MT586586	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Australia
MT586585	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586588	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586587	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2017	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
LR584021	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	-	-	-
MT586577	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586578	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
LR584019	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	-	-	-
MT586579	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Australia
LR584020	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	-	-	-
MT586580	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586589	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Lens culinaris</i>	Australia
MT586590	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
LR584026	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	-	-	-
LR584027	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	-	-	-
LR584025	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	-	-	-
MT586584	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586583	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2015	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Australia
MW537050	BrYV	TuYV	BrYV	2017	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	Philippines
OK030793	TuYV	TuYV	BrYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
KF923236	BrYV	TuYV	BrYV		<i>Brassica rapa var.</i>	
				2011	<i>pekinensis</i>	South Korea
X13063	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	-	-	-
NC_003743	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	-	-	-
MT586597	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2018	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586598	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2018	<i>Beta vulgaris</i>	Australia
OK030772	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030770	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MN497809	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MN497800	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
Pers comm Roxana Hossain	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	-	<i>Beta vulgaris</i>	Netherlands
OK030789	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030794	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2007	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030773	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030774	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030780	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MN497806	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2017	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MN497807	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2018	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MN497805	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MN497802	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2018	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany

OK030750	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030782	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030767	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030783	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
OK030778	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MN497811	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2018	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MK450519	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2006	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	Germany
MW854285	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	-	<i>Physalis pubescens</i>	Germany
KU198395	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2014	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	South Africa
MT586591	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586594	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2014	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586593	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
MT586592	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2012	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
OK030781	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MZ442681	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	Turkey
MZ442680	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	Turkey
MZ442679	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	Turkey
MN497804	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2018	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
OK030790	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2019	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	United Kingdom
MN497801	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2017	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MK450520	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2016	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Germany
MT955607	BrYV	TuYV	TuYV	2018	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Greece
MT586595	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2016	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Australia
LR584024	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	-	-	-
JQ862472	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2011	<i>Diuris sp.</i>	Australia
MT586596	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2015	<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	Australia
KU726091	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2014	<i>Arachis pintoi</i>	Colombia
KU726090	TuYV	TuYV	TuYV	2014	<i>Arachis pintoi</i>	Colombia
